

1	Comprehensible delivery of essential information
Name	Comprehensible delivery of essential information
Description	<p>All essential information for the users in the process (i.e. all interactions related to the service and ID application) should be presented in a complete, target group-orientated and comprehensible manner to facilitate and support use.</p> <p>In particular, before the process starts, users must be provided with information about the description of the process and its functional and technical requirements for successful completion in order to avoid process cancellation or frustration on the part of the users.</p>
User experience attribute(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability • Accessibility • Findability
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the processes in detail and in different ways (video, text, chatbot, etc.) • Provide prerequisite information (technical and organizational) required for the successful completion of the process • Provide relevant information to data protection, such as presentation of data processing and compliance with the data protection standard. • Provide relevant information to security, such as compliance with security standards and contextual assistance • Provide easy-to-access context-sensitive help (e.g. using UI elements such as tooltips)
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essential information such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Credentials that must be available digitally to use them in the process • Where can these credentials be requested • Overview of compatible wallets • Overview of compatible operating systems • Information on wallet download (e.g. supported operating systems, information on the app stores, version number, etc.) • Types of information provided such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explanation videos • FAQs • Introduction wizard / onboarding information • Provide screens of the wallet (preview images)
Exemplary advantages that arise from the application of heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple onboarding of new users • Facilitate and support use • Avoid process cancellation or frustration on the part of users
Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidance, Workload (Bastien, C., Scapin, D. 1993. Ergonomic criteria for the evaluation of human-computer interfaces.) • Information, Understanding (Boucher, A. 2020. Ergonomie web.) • Clear goals, Focused concentration (Colombo, L., Pasch, M. 2012. 10 Heuristics for an Optimal User Experience.) • Erlernbarkeit, Robustheit gegen Benutzungsfehler (DIN EN ISO 9241-110, Ergonomie der Mensch-System-Interaktion. 2020. https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/3147467) • Recognition rather than recall, Help and Documentation (Nielsen, J. 1994. Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/191666.19172) • Khayretdinova, A., Kubach, M., Sellung, R., Roßnagel, H. 2022. Conducting a Usability Evaluation of Decentralized Identity Management Solutions. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-33306-5_19 • Sauer, M., Pfeifer, S., Sürmeli, J., Siebert, E., Woytal, I. 2024. User-friendly Integration of Identity Wallets and Mobility Platforms: A User Experience Study Conducted in the SDIKA Project. http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12412.55682

ID	2
Name	Support for informed decision-making
Description	<p>Users should be supported in making informed decisions.</p> <p>This is particularly important for processes that have a high barrier to entry; e.g. due to novelty, lack of expertise or negative previous experience with similar applications, supporting information should be provided at the appropriate time. This should enable users to make informed decisions about the process and the use of the technology.</p>
User experience attribute(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utility • Credibility
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide support to make informed decisions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compare the conventional (e.g. analog) and new solution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show the advantage of the process and the new technology(ies) • Present the ID application(s) required for the process and show the differences between the applications (e.g. different wallets) • Provide recommended actions for users in the context of sending data (data request) • Provide recommended actions for users in the context of storing credentials (credential offer)
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed decision on usage of technology: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advantages and disadvantages of the online process (time, effort, etc.) or the alternative process • Description of alternative uses for a wallet (aside of current process) • Description of alternative uses for an issued credential • Informed decision about a specific application: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of compatible wallets and their differences, e.g. price and supported service providers (interoperability) • Informed decisions while using a specific application: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic light system for data requests shows recommended action for users regarding the sending of their data (e.g. on the basis of purpose of the request) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green= Sending the data is recommended; • Yellow= User's own judgement; • Red= Sending the data is not recommended
Exemplary advantages that arise from the application of heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dispelling users' reservations and fears • Communicate motivation and benefits for users • During the individual process steps, users receive all the information that enables them to choose between different options within the process • Digital sovereignty
Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the user's activities — do not force., Provide utility matching with the user's values. (Arhippainen, L. 2013. A Tutorial of Ten User Experience Heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/2523429.2523491) • Guidance (Bastien, C., Scapin, D. 1993. Ergonomic criteria for the evaluation of human-computer interfaces.) • Challenges/skills balance, Potential control, Know thy user's motivations, Help, Speed (Colombo, L., Pasch, M. 2012. 10 Heuristics for an Optimal User Experience.) • Benutzerbindung, Steuerbarkeit (DIN EN ISO 9241-110, Ergonomie der Mensch-System-Interaktion. 2020. https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/3147467) • Help and documentation (Nielsen, J. 1994. Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/191666.19172) • Khayretdinova, A., Kubach, M., Sellung, R., Roßnagel, H. 2022. Conducting a Usability Evaluation of Decentralized Identity Management Solutions. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-33306-5_19

ID	3
Name	Target group-oriented and standardized terminology
Description	The technical terms or terminology used should be consistent throughout the entire process, appropriate to the target group and across all applications. Already established technical terms within the industry should be adopted . However, it should always be checked whether it is necessary to confront users with the use of (certain) technical terms.
User experience attribute(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability • Accessibility
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use common language that is suitable for the target group (e.g. laypersons) • If technical terms have to be used, the (new) unfamiliar terms must be explained <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use standardized definitions within the context of a domain (e.g. SSI / an ID ecosystem) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If non-existent, define terms and check comprehensibility with target groups • Use the same terms consistently (within the same service and same domain)
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential technical terms to be clarified: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trustworthy • Verified • Encrypted • ID • Wallet • Sending data vs. data sharing
Exemplary advantages that arise from the application of heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good comprehensibility of information for users • High memorability and recognizability of standardized terms • Standardized terms make new applications easy to learn
Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect the user. (Arhippainen, L. 2013. A Tutorial of Ten User Experience Heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/2523429.2523491) • Consistency, Compatibility (Bastien, C., Scapin, D. 1993. Ergonomic criteria for the evaluation of human-computer interfaces.) • Information, Understanding (Boucher, A. 2020. Ergonomie web.) • Challenges/skills balance (Colombo, L., Pasch, M. 2012. 10 Heuristics for an Optimal User Experience.) • Erwartungskonformität (DIN EN ISO 9241-110, Ergonomie der Mensch-System-Interaktion. 2020. https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/3147467) • Consistency, Language (Kaniasty, E. CARMEL UX Guidelines & Criteria. https://www.slipperstudios.com/services/carmel-ux-full/) • Match Between the System and the Real World, Consistency and Standards (Nielsen, J. 1994. Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/191666.19172) • Strive for consistency (Shneiderman, B., Plaisant, C., Cohen, M., Jacobs, S., Elmqvist, N. 2016. Designing the User Interface: Strategies for Effective Human-Computer Interaction) • BA-07-Konsistente Sprache, BA-08 – Benutzungsfreundliche Terminologie und Metaphern (Krauß, A.-M., Sellung, R.A., Kostic, S. 2023. Ist das die Wallet der Zukunft? https://doi.org/10.1365/s40702-023-00952-6) • Sartor, S., Sedlmeir, J., Rieger, A., Roth, T. 2022. Love at First Sight? A User Experience Study of Self-Sovereign Identity Wallets. • Sauer, M., Pfeifer, S., Sürmeli, J., Siebert, E., Woytal, I. 2024. User-friendly Integration of Identity Wallets and Mobility Platforms: A User Experience Study Conducted in the SDIKA Project. http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12412.55682

Name	4
Description	<p>Holistic process support</p> <p>The entire process - from initial interaction to completion - should be viewed as a coherent whole and developed in a user-friendly and memorable way. Complex processes can be simplified through good user guidance. Users should be guided and supported across all applications (i.e. ID and service provider applications) in order to minimize cognitive load and avoid or correct errors during use. This also includes consideration of the usage situation and context (goals, tasks, environment, user, resources).</p>
User experience attribute(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usability
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Take user requirements into account, e.g. need for multiple device use, offline capability when carrying out processes (without Internet access) Interaction: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of familiar and expectation-compliant interaction patterns <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guarantee a similar flow of user interactions in the process (user flow) regardless of the technologies used For actions that require several devices, it should be made clear to users on which device the specific action is to be carried out. Interaction between the service provider (e.g. website) and ID application (e.g. wallet) should be supported by redirect links and automatic redirects. The display of the supported technology should be context-based: e.g. if a mobile browser is used, the redirect link should be highlighted, but the QR code should not be excluded here (differentiation between one or more devices during use) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> QR-Code can be generated and displayed if required Successful actions and the general status must be visible through corresponding feedback on both devices (in the case of multi-device use). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The same status must be displayed on all devices ID application: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Credentials should be preselected automatically <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suggestion of credentials to be present, which are compatible or suitable (in combination) It should be made clear to users that an alternative credential is equally compatible (if an alternative is available)
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Process information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status is displayed at which process step the users are currently at Information about the digital credentials required to use the service <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Where and how can the required credentials be applied for digitally (via link)? Data is sent - feedback should appear in wallet and on website The process does not end when the credential is issued, but provides information about the possible uses of the credential afterwards Context of use: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognition of the device and associated interactions (e.g. display of a forwarding link to the wallet only for mobile devices) Enable synchronization of the wallet across multiple devices (multi-device use) Possibility to switch from the wallet back to the service provider's app Be able to present credentials from wallet without Internet access To avoid errors, users are displayed a selection of credentials that meet the requirements of the service, which they can present to service providers.
Exemplary advantages that arise from the application of heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consistent, continuous user experience even when changing context (e.g. transition from desktop to mobile device) Efficient use due to automatic forwarding when changing context on the same device Lower cognitive load
Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design the product or service to fit the intended contexts. (Ariippainen, L. 2013. A Tutorial of Ten User Experience Heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/2421490.2421501) Guidance, Adaptability, Error Management (Bastien, C. Scapin, D. 1993. Ergonomic criteria for the evaluation of human-computer interfaces.) User Satisfaction, Error Control, Logic, Architecture (Boucher, A. 2020. Ergonomie web.) Clear goals, Focused concentration, Ergonomical transparency, Challenges/skills balance, Follow the rhythm (Colombo, L., Pasch, M. 2012. 10 Heuristics for an Optimal User Experience.) Aufgabenangemessenheit, Erlernbarkeit, Robustheit gegen Benutzungsfehler (DIN EN ISO 9241-110, Ergonomie der Mensch-System-Interaktion. 2020. https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/1147467) Recovery, Efficiency (Kaniasty, E. CARMEL UX Guidelines & Criteria. https://www.silpocentstudios.com/services/carmel-ux-full/) Help and documentation, Error Prevention, Help Users Recognize, Diagnose, and Recover from Errors (Nielsen, J. 1994. Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/191866.191723) 4. Design dialogs to yield closure, 5. Prevent errors (Shneiderman, B., Plaisant, C., Cohen, M., Jacobs, S., Elmqvist, N. 2016. Designing the User Interface: Strategies for Effective Human-Computer Interaction) Krauß, A.-M., Sellung, R.A., Kostic, S. 2023. Ist das die Wallet der Zukunft? https://doi.org/10.1365/04709-021-00952-6 Ebert, S., Krauß, A.-M., Anke, J. 2023. Towards informed choices: A decision model for adaptive warnings in self-sovereign identity. https://doi.org/10.38438/muc2023-mci-ws11-322 Santor, S., Sedlmeir, J., Rieger, A., Roth, T. 2022. Love at First Sight? A User Experience Study of Self-Sovereign Identity Wallets. Sauer, M., Pfeifer, S., Sömmel, J., Siebert, E., Woytal, I. 2024. User-friendly Integration of Identity Wallets and Mobility Platforms: A User Experience Study Conducted in the SOIRA Project. https://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12412.55882

Name	5
Description	<p>Transparency</p> <p>Relevant information should always be presented transparently for users. This includes, in particular, the current status of the system (e.g. success and failure messages, fulfilment degree in the process with the parties involved) as well as missing data, authorisations and data processing.</p>
User experience attribute(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability • Credibility
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency with regard to process information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make progress in the process visible to users • Show current system and process status (success/failure messages (feedback)) • Show interactions with service providers in the ID application and the data sent/received • Show missing credentials in the ID application <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show use case-dependent, missing credentials or credential attributes (including those that do not fulfil the trust level) • Show options for issuing missing credentials and credential attributes • Transparency in terms of security: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Display service providers and their trustworthiness (e.g. is verified?) through automated evaluation • Present authorizations of the service providers, e.g. for the trust level of requested credentials, if necessary show authorization certificate • Transparently list data to be sent from the credentials and their levels of assurance • Present details on data processing transparently (for what purpose and what happens to the data after the confirmed data request?) • Make it possible to compare the data request in the ID application with the one on the service provider's application (users should be given the opportunity to compare the data request: Is this the same request, is the same data being requested, etc.)
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency with regard to process information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback after successful user actions (e.g. message when credential has been successfully stored in wallet) • History of interactions performed • Display in the data request if the required credential in the wallet does not have the level of assurance required by the service provider (e.g. stored student ID card instead of a required ID document) • Transparency in terms of security: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wallet warns users if they want to present credentials with too high a level of trust that is not necessary and suggests more appropriate credential(s) • Display how data of users and where data in the wallet and by the service provider is stored • Display the data transfer to third parties • Display the duration of data storage by the service provider / third parties • Display of the same overview of the requested data in the wallet and on the service provider's website for the purpose of cross-checking
Examples of the advantages that arise from the application of heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing trust in the system and its credibility • Strengthening the conscious handling of data
Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency (Allen, C. 2016. The Path to Self-Sovereign Identity. https://www.lifewithalacrity.com/article/the-path-to-self-sovereign-identity/) • Guidance (Bastien, C., Scapin, D. 1993. Ergonomic criteria for the evaluation of human-computer interfaces.) • Information (Boucher, A. 2020. Ergonomie web.) • Appropriate feedback (Colombo, L., Pasch, M. 2012. 10 Heuristics for an Optimal User Experience.) • Selbstbeschreibungsfähigkeit (DIN EN ISO 9241-110, Ergonomie der Mensch-System-Interaktion. 2020. https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/3147467) • Recovery, Memory (Kaniasty, E. CARMEL UX Guidelines & Criteria. https://www.sliiperstudios.com/services/carmel-ux-full/) • Visibility of System status (Nielsen, J. 1994. Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/191666.191772) • Guideline 1.2, Guideline 2.1 (Shneiderman, B. 2000. Designing trust into online experiences. https://doi.org/10.1145/355112.355124) • Informative Feedback (Shneiderman, B., Plaisant, C., Cohen, M., Jacobs, S., Elmqvist, N. 2016. Designing the User Interface: Strategies for Effective Human-Computer Interaction) • BA-10 – Transparenz (Krauß, A.-M., Sellung, R.A., Kostic, S. 2023. Ist das die Wallet der Zukunft? https://doi.org/10.1365/4-80702-023-00952-6) • Lennartsson, M., Kävrestad, J., Nohlberg, M. 202). Exploring the meaning of usable security - a literature review. https://doi.org/10.1108/ICS-10-2020-0167 • Sauer, M., Pfeiffer, S., Sürmel, J., Siebert, E., Woytal, I. 2024. User-friendly Integration of Identity Wallets and Mobility Platforms: A User Experience Study Conducted in the SDIKA Project. http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12412.55682

ID	6
Name	Accessible interaction and inclusion
Description	Interaction with the applications throughout the entire process should be implemented without barriers , especially for use across multiple devices or when changing context within a device. In addition, at least one alternative process (e.g. analog) should be offered, especially in the introductory phase of the new technology, so that no one is excluded from using the service.
User experience attribute(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to the process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comply with accessibility criteria (see EN 301 549 V3 the harmonized European Standard for ICT Accessibility) • Provide Easy Read • Provide multiple-language support • Offer alternative(s) to the process with the new technology (e.g. continue to offer analog process) • Regarding technology: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider different devices and device changes (for multiple device use) • Offer various authentication procedures, in particular for unlocking the ID application and presenting credentials
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regarding the UI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use sufficient contrast so that people with visual impairments are not excluded • Offer Screen reader support • Voice control support • Offering alternatives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process alternatives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analog process (on site, mail) • Digital process with PDF documents • Different authentication procedures • Use of accessible alternatives to classic QR codes (talking, beeper QR codes, smart QR codes, A-QR codes, redirect links) for multi-device use
Examples of the advantages that arise from the application of heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion • Larger user group • Users feel that they and their needs are recognized
Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide several ways to interact, leave choice for the user. (Arhippainen, L. 2013. A Tutorial of Ten User Experience Heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/2523429.2523491) • Accessibility (Boucher, A. 2020. Ergonomie web.) • ETSI. 2021. Harmonisierte Europäische Norm (EN) 301 549 - Accessibility requirements for ICT products and services. • Accessibility (Kaniasty, E. CARMEL UX Guidelines & Criteria. https://www.slipperstudios.com/services/carmel-ux-full/) • Seek universal usability (Shneiderman, B., Plaisant, C., Cohen, M., Jacobs, S., Elmqvist, N. 2016. Designing the User Interface: Strategies for Effective Human-Computer Interaction) • W3C. 2024. Web Content Accessibility Guidelines. • BA-13 – Zugänglichkeit (Krauß, A.-M., Sellung, R.A., Kostic, S. 2023. Ist das die Wallet der Zukunft? https://doi.org/10.1365/s40702-023-00952-6) • Initiative D21 e. V. 2024. D21-Digital-Index 2023/2024. https://initiatived21.de/publikationen/d21-digital-index/2023-24 • Kudra, A., 2022, Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) in Deutschland. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11623-022-1555-1

ID	7
Name	Customizability according to security needs
Description	Users should be able to configure the application individually in a user-friendly way, depending on their security requirements in order to create a customized balance between user experience and security.
User experience attribute(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability • Credibility
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable various authentication procedures for access to the ID application • Enable customized security configurations when presenting, receiving and saving credentials (depending on credentials, data sent, use cases and service providers) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Granting permanent authorizations (e.g. for frequently repeating actions) • Set up additional authentication • Enable blocking of unverified / unauthorized service providers • Enable configuration of individual warning messages • Provide options for creating and restoring backups to restore the ID application.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decision-making sovereignty: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual authentication procedures depending on credentials, data sent, use cases and service providers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optional additional protection, such as biometrics, upon presentation of certain credentials • Different authentication procedures for unlocking the wallet • Possibility to automatically deselect optional data in the data request • Convenience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users can decide whether to automatically accept certain authorization offers (permanent authorizations) • Users can decide whether to automatically present certain credentials to certain service providers for certain use cases (permanent authorizations) • Create a backup
Examples of the advantages that arise from the application of heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User loyalty • Identification with the application • Increase trust in the application
Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptability (Bastien, C., Scapin, D. 1993. Ergonomic criteria for the evaluation of human-computer interfaces.) • Freedom (Boucher, A. 2020. Ergonomie web.) • Respect the user's privacy and security. (Arhippainen, L. 2013. A Tutorial of Ten User Experience Heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/2523429.2523491) • Technology appropriation (Colombo, L., Pasch, M. 2012. 10 Heuristics for an Optimal User Experience.) • Steuerbarkeit (DIN EN ISO 9241-110, Ergonomie der Mensch-System-Interaktion. 2020. https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/3147467) • Recovery (Kaniasty, E. CARMEL UX Guidelines & Criteria. https://www.slipperstudios.com/services/carmel-ux-full/) • Individualisierbarkeit, Flexibility and Efficiency of Use (Nielsen, J. 1994. Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/191666.19172) • Seek universal usability (Shneiderman, B., Plaisant, C., Cohen, M., Jacobs, S., Elmquist, N. 2016. Designing the User Interface: Strategies for Effective Human-Computer Interaction) • Krauß, A.-M., Sellung, R.A., Kostic, S. 2023. Ist das die Wallet der Zukunft? https://doi.org/10.1365/s40702-023-00952-6 • Kostic, S., Poikela, M. 2022. Do Users Want To Use Digital Identities? A Study Of A Concept Of An Identity Wallet • Sauer, M., Pfeifer, S., Sürmeli, J., Siebert, E., Woytal, I. 2024. User-friendly Integration of Identity Wallets and Mobility Platforms: A User Experience Study Conducted in the SDIKA Project. http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12412.55682

Name	B
Description	<p>User Sovereignty</p> <p>Every action requires the consent of the user in order to maintain their sovereignty.</p> <p>Users should be able to carry out actions at their own pace and under their own conditions.</p> <p>In addition, they should be able to cancel, repeat or revoke actions at any time.</p> <p>Applications (e.g. wallets, etc.) and credentials should be as interoperable as possible for users so that they are not restricted to one application and isolated identities do not arise.</p>
User experience attribute(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usability Value
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User decision: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leave it to users to decide whether or not to send their data Leave it to the users to decide which compatible credential(s) to use to send the data Allow the users to undo, pause and repeat actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allow the users to revoke the ID application's permanent authorizations Allow the users to withdraw sent data Offer a general option to cancel the process Create interoperability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> When issuing credentials, standardized schemes should be used so that the credentials are recognized by as many service providers as possible. Users should be given the option of quickly and easily switching (e.g. from backup) to other ID applications with their data.
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User decision: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data is only sent if users actively consent to it Users can decide not to send optionally requested data Users can pause the request for data and continue it later Allow undo and redo in the process flow Re-initiate actions, such as presentation or acceptance of proof, in case of failure Revoke presented credentials Users can reset their wallet Interoperability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Users can choose between different wallets and switch between them at any time
Examples of the advantages that arise from the application of heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhancing sovereignty <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Giving users control over their data and the application (data sovereignty) Enabling users to choose between several alternatives with similar hardware and software performance (technological sovereignty) A sense of trust is encouraged
Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control (Allen, C. 2016. The Path to Self-Sovereign Identity. https://www.lifewithalacrity.com/article/the-path-to-self-sovereign-identity/) User Control and Freedom (Nielsen, J. 1994. Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/191666.19172) Sartor, S., Sedlmeir, J., Rieger, A., Roth, T. 2022. Love at First Sight? A User Experience Study of Self-Sovereign Identity Wallets. Freedom (Boucher, A. 2020. Ergonomie web.) Respect the user's privacy and security., Support the user's activities — do not force. (Arhippainen, L. 2013. A Tutorial of Ten User Experience Heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/2523429.2523491) Explicit Control (Bastien, C., Scapin, D. 1993. Ergonomic criteria for the evaluation of human-computer interfaces.) Potential control, Follow the rhythm (Colombo, L., Pasch, M. 2012. 10 Heuristics for an Optimal User Experience.) Steuerbarkeit (DIN EN ISO 9241-110, Ergonomie der Mensch-System-Interaktion. 2020. https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/3147467) Permit easy reversal of actions, Keep users in control (Shneiderman, B., Plaisant, C., Cohen, M., Jacobs, S., Elmquist, N. 2016. Designing the User Interface: Strategies for Effective Human-Computer Interaction) BA-04- Befähigte Nutzende (Krauß, A.-M., Sellung, R.A., Kostic, S. 2023. Ist das die Wallet der Zukunft? https://doi.org/10.1365/s40702-023-00952-6) Sellung, R., Kubach, M. 2023. Research on User Experience for Digital IdentityWallets: State-of-the-Art and Recommendations. 2023. https://doi.org/10.18420/OID2023_03 Sovrin Foundation. 2023. Principles Of SSI V3. https://sovrin.org/principles-of-ssi/

	9
Name	Maintaining data protection and privacy
Description	Users must be informed of their rights regarding their data in a user-friendly and comprehensible way and must also be able to apply them. In addition, the principle of data minimization should come into effect.
User experience attribute(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Credibility • Usability
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement the GDPR in a user-friendly and comprehensible way <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comply with disclosure obligations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indicate the purpose of the data collection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the purpose as specific as possible and as broadly (extensively) as necessary • Present the authorizations of the service providers, e.g. for the level of assurance of requested credentials, and present the authorisation certificate if necessary • Display and describe details of data processing and storage (what happens to the data after the confirmed data request?), in particular from third-party providers • Inform users about their rights • Give users the opportunity to exercise their right of access (by the data subject) • Give users the opportunity to exercise their right to rectification • Give users the opportunity to exercise their right to have their data deleted and to be forgotten • Obtain user consent for data processing • Follow the principle of data minimization when interacting with users <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data requests with minimum necessary data • Optional data can be sent if users wish • Give users the opportunity to report service providers • Credentials should be automatically preselected <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The credential that fulfills the requirements should always be requested with the lowest possible level of assurance. • Use comprehensible language and icons/symbols in addition to legal texts to make data protection statements easier to understand
Example	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR-related: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data is only sent if users actively agree • Right of access by the data subject: Direct contact, e.g. via a contact person, must be possible • If users have reason to suspect that service providers are not authorized to request data, users should be able to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report this service • Withdraw the sent data • Sent data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow users to send only the claim that they are of legal age and not the date of birth (zero knowledge) • Help users to send only individual attributes and make it clear that only individual attributes and not the entire credential has to be sent (selective disclosure to implement minimal disclosure) • Allow users to specify an expiration date for the credentials presented to the service provider
Examples of the advantages that arise from the application of heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection of user privacy • Increase in user trust
Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access, Protection, Minimisation (Allen, C. 2016. The Path to Self-Sovereign Identity. https://www.lifewithalacrity.com/article/the-path-to-self-sovereign-identity/) • Respect the user's privacy and security. (Arhippainen, L. 2013. A Tutorial of Ten User Experience Heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/2523429.2523491) • Freedom (Boucher, A. 2020. Ergonomie web.) • Potential control (Colombo, L., Pasch, M. 2012. 10 Heuristics for an Optimal User Experience.) • User Control and Freedom (Nielsen, J. 1994. Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/191666.191722) • Guideline 1.4, Guideline 2.2 (Shneiderman, B. 2000. Designing trust into online experiences. https://doi.org/10.1145/355112.355124) • Europäische Union. 2016. Datenschutz-Grundverordnung. • Hempel, G., Anke, J. 2023 Privacy Management mit Self-Sovereign Identity: Potenziale zur Erhöhung der informationellen Selbstbestimmung. https://doi.org/10.5771/9783748938743-399

ID	10
Name	Aesthetic, focused and trust-building design
Description	When designing applications, it is important to ensure that content and design focus on the essentials and provide users with the best possible support in achieving their goals with the applications. In addition, designs should ensure that security is made usable and understandable so that users have trust in the applications.
User experience attribute(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desirability • Usability • Findability • Accessibility • Credibility
Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement simple, clear, minimalistic and consistent designs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use designs that focus on relevant content • Use consistent colors, typography and style elements • Use cross-application, standardized, established, well-known and accessible design patterns • Use bright patterns (prioritizing users' goals and well-being) instead of dark patterns (prioritizing the interests of e.g. the company over those of the users and making them do something they didn't want to do) • Use modern and contemporary design
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Display only information that is relevant for users and current actions. • Use recurring, application-independent design patterns for service providers and wallets. • Encourage users through the design not to take any actions that could compromise security, e.g. highlighting a button to refuse to present a credential with non-verified service providers (no dark patterns). • Use of icons consistently throughout the entire service and ID application
Examples of the advantages that arise from the application of heuristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User engagement • Identification with the application • Increase trust in the application • Increase security • Contributes to inclusion
Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go for a perfect visual design. (Arhippainen, L. 2013. A Tutorial of Ten User Experience Heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/2523429.2523491) • Workload (Bastien, C., Scapin, D. 1993. Ergonomic criteria for the evaluation of human-computer interfaces.) • Visual Organization, Architecture (Boucher, A. 2020. Ergonomie web.) • Focused concentration (Colombo, L., Pasch, M. 2012. 10 Heuristics for an Optimal User Experience.) • Domingo, M. 2020. Dieter Rams: 10 Timeless Commandments for Good Design. https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/dieter-rams-10-timeless-commandments-for-good-design • Consistency, Accessibility, Efficiency (Kaniasty, E. CARMEL UX Guidelines & Criteria. https://www.slipperstudios.com/services/carmel-ux-full/) • Aesthetic and minimalist design, Flexibility and Efficiency of Use (Nielsen, J. 1994. Enhancing the explanatory power of usability heuristics. https://doi.org/10.1145/191666.19172) • Strive for consistency (Shneiderman, B., Plaisant, C., Cohen, M., Jacobs, S., Elmqvist, N. 2016. Designing the User Interface: Strategies for Effective Human-Computer Interaction) • Conducting a Usability Evaluation of Decentralized Identity Management Solutions, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-33306-5_19 • Richter, D., Krauß, A.-M., Ebert, S., Handke, S. 2023. On the Search for Trust: Self-Sovereign Identity and the Public Sector. https://doi.org/10.18420/rvi2023-024 • Sartor, S., Sedlmeir, J., Rieger, A., Roth, T. 2022. Love at First Sight? A User Experience Study of Self-Sovereign Identity Wallets.